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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

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Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'

Kasthuri P. K.¹

Abstract

Modern law strictly orders the protection of surrendered soldiers in war. However, from the perspective of *Pancatantram*, a miniature treatise of Statecraft strongly emphasizes that an hors de combat must be slayed without any consideration as there are many risks of taking refuge. This study aims to discover the reasons behind the fear of trusting a surrendered enemy with some historical incidents. The surrender of an enemy army or even a defeated king cannot be accepted as trustworthy, as there is no surety of loyalty forever, and it is not practical to monitor them all the time.

Keywords: Kingship - Hors de combat - *Pancatantram* - *Kakolukiyam* - Policy of Duplicity.

Introduction

Kingship is a mighty position that includes very complicated responsibilities to be decided and dealt with highly intellectually. A king has to handle the Law, Governance, Welfare of the people, International affairs, Economic stability, Protection of the country, Provision of Justice and other limitless duties. In matters of war and enemy, a king must be very cautious to handle because it may destroy his rule and his kingdom. Even after defeating the enemy army, many other possibilities exist for losing power. One of those is to have an enemy within the territory.

Hors de combat is a person on the enemy side who surrenders due to any injury or detention or any other cause and gives up his weapons. The present law states that the person who surrenders due to sickness, detention or any other cause shall, in all circumstances, be treated humanely (Sassoli et al., 2014). But, In *Pancatantram*, it is

1 . Research Scholar, Department of Sanskrit, Madurai Kamaraj University.

dealt with differently that one should not spare the surrenderer alive.

Dealing with an hors de combat:

In the minds of political people, though the surrenderer proves completely loyal, trusting him completely is always a matter of discussion. The Ramayana has such an incident when Vibhisana surrenders to Lord Rama. Sugriva argues to refuse him because he is the brother of the enemy Ravana and may slay all of them as the owl killed the crows.

प्रविष्टः शत्रु सैन्यं हि प्राप्तः शत्रुरतर्कितः ।

निहन्यादन्तरं लब्ध्वा उलूको वायसानिव ॥ (Arya 2004: 35)

A similar story is written in the third book of *Pancatantram* titled “*kakolukiyam*”, which describes the duplicity act of an old crow minister who wins the trust of the owl king and wipes out the entire parliament of owls with fire in the right situation as the perfect revenge for the massacre of crows by owls. In Ramayana, the owl is depicted as a surrenderer who would kill all crows. However, in *Pancatantram*, a crow, weaker than an owl, is depicted to firmly establish the power of duplicity.

Pancatantram is a Sanskrit text written by Vishnu Sarma, a scholar in Political science appointed by King Amarasakti to train three foolish princes about statecraft in a short period of six months. The text describes the loss and gaining of friendship in the first two books, respectively. The third book *Kakolukiyam* consists of the policy of duplicity for the complete destruction of a foe that is beyond the destruction created by war.

शस्त्रैर्हता न हि हता रिपवो भवन्ति प्रज्ञाहतास्तु रिपवः सुहताः भवन्ति ।

शस्त्रं निहन्ति पुरुषस्य शरीरमेकं प्रज्ञा कुलं च विभवं च यशश्च हन्ति ॥

(Jha 2021: 526)

The above verse strongly suggests the political insight to destroy the enemies, which can annihilate the community, wealth and glory, whereas weapons in war can just destroy their bodies.

The third book starts with the complete negation of accepting a surrendered hostile, and to prove the policy, the story of owls and crows begins then. In a southern city named Mahilaropya, there was a huge banyan tree where the crow king named Meghavarna lived with his murder of crows. Likewise, Arimardana, king of owls, lived in a cave on a mountain with his parliament of owls. Due to

hereditary animosity, Arimardana and his retinue slayed crows in the tree during nighttime. This is due to the negligence of enemies.

य उपेक्षेत शत्रुं स्वं प्रसरन्तं यदृच्छया ।

रोगं चालस्य-संयुक्तः स शनैस् तेन हन्यते ॥ (Jha 2021: 400)

For retaliation, Meghavarna discussed with his ministers. After hearing *Sadagunya* measures (the six attributes of statecraft) such as *Sandhi* (Peace), *Vigraha* (War), *Yana* (Escape), *Asana* (Stationing in the fort), *Samsraya* (Resorting to a mighty friend) and *Dvaitibhava* (Duplicity) of ministers, the king accepted the plan of duplicity by Sthirajivi. He started a fake quarrel, false injury to Sthirajivi and escaped to Rsyamuka mountain along with his retinue as instructed by Sthirajivi. Arimardhana was informed by his spy about the enemy's escape and rushed to the banyan tree, the enemy fort. He found the minister Sthirajivi wounded badly and abandoned.

Sthirajivi deceitfully explained the reason for his plight was that he advised Meghavarna not to fight against Arimardana, who is mightier, and expressed his anger towards Meghavarna as after recovery of wounds, he shall accompany Arimardana to the residence of Crows for destruction. Except for Minister Raktaksa, all other ministers of Arimardana support providing shelter to Sthirajivi, and the king decides the same as the majority. Sthirajivi sheltered in the cave entrance, collected plenty of dry sticks and secretly informed Meghavarna to burn the cave by instructing every crow to bring and burn with a burning stick in the daytime as the owls are day-blinded. After destroying the owls into ashes, all the crows returned to their old fort, i.e., the huge banyan tree and lived happily.

This story strongly emphasizes the non-acceptance of an enemy as a friend in any circumstance. Even Sthirajivi appreciates Raktaksa within his heart as the true minister of Arimardana.

हन्यतामिति येनोक्तं स्वामिनो हितवादिना ।

स एवैकोऽत्र सर्वेषां नीतिशास्त्राऽर्थतत्त्ववित् ॥ (Jha 2021: 501)

Sthirajivi considers Raktaksa, who suggested killing Sthirajivi, as the only faithful minister of Arimardana, a knower of political science, and all others are merely fools. He considers the one who believes a former enemy is trustworthy as just an unfortunate person. Similarly, Vidura describes the same as a fool.

अमित्रं कुरुते मित्रं मित्रं द्वेष्टि हिनस्ति च ।

कर्म चारभते दुष्टं तमाहुर्मूढचेतसम् ॥ (Menon 1955: 16)

There are some valid reasons for Raktaksa to suggest slaying the surrendered enemy, which the enemy even praises in his mind. There are many types of surrenders, such as *Saranagati* (seeking refuge to a higher power), *Samarpana* (Dedication of one's action to a supreme one), *Atma-Nivedana* (Surrender of one's own soul), *Prapatti* (Complete surrender to god and accepting upcoming happenings as God's wish), *Tyaga* (surrender of material possession). But if an enemy surrenders, many risks can happen if the enemy is in a king's retinue.

First of all, accepting an enemy as one among them is stressful. Though one can trust the enemy and his valid reason for surrender, inner peace would indeed be disturbed due to fear of secrecy leakage and unexpected attack. Sthirajivi expressed this tension with an example as,

निःसर्पे, हतसर्पे वा, भवने सुप्तये सुखम् ।

दृष्टनष्टभुजङ्गे तु निद्रा दुःखेन लभ्यते ॥ (Jha 2021: 529)

An enemy surrenders and turns out to be a friend like a snake that is seen and missed because there will be sleep loss due to restlessness and fear, whereas a house freed from a snake or killed is vice versa. The enemy may spy secretly and inform his master, and it is entirely impossible to monitor all the time.

Secondly, a servant of an enemy approaches as a surrenderer and may be wicked as if he is true, he is cheating his master, and if he is deceitful, he serves as a spy and surely informs the appropriate time and place to destroy. If a person truthfully hates his master and surrenders, there must be a gain from the opposition he expects; for that, only he is willing to disclose the secrets of his former master.

Loyalty towards one's country and race is much stronger than another. In the 18th century AD, James Armistead Lafayette was a well-known double spy who was an American, after being defeated by Britain, working as a spy for them. But he gave false information to Britain and secretly sent the proper information to the American Government. It is also stated in *Pancatantram* that a person would be more loyal to their own race.

सूर्यं भर्तारमुत्सृज्य, पर्जन्यं, मारुतं, गिरिम् ।

स्वजातिं मूषिका प्राप्ता, स्वजातिर्दुरतिक्रमा ॥ (Jha 2021: 494)

To prove the attachment of every person to their race, there is a story of a She-mouse who accepted a mouse as more suitable for her to marry after rejecting even Celestial Gods such as Surya, Parjanya, Maruta and a Mountain. In Ramayana, Vibhisana stayed loyal to Rama and acquired coronation after the assassination of King Ravana. But, in Mahabharata, Vikarna, Brother of Duryodhana, spoke against Gambling and torture to Draupati and stood on the side of his own brother in war even though he knew that he was on the side of immorality. Even unrighteousness, it is pretty common to be on the side of one's own race; blood is always thicker than water.

There are many instances where weaker emperors surrendered to stronger ones with a rivalry in heart and a desire to defeat the stronger king to emerge their independence. Maharana Pratap was a powerful Rajput king defeated by Mughals in the battle of Haldighati in 1576. He escaped secretly to the mountains and continued the Guerrilla war against the Mughals. Man Singh I, Akbar's General, convinced him to be a vassal king and made Pratap's brother Shakti Singh seated in the Mughal court. But Shakti Singh secretly delivered the happenings of the Mughal court for his brother. That is why the emperor should be vigilant of spies, unexpected revolts of independence, etc., and fear trusting any surrender from the enemy side and placing him in his entourage.

When trusted, the king may get some information about the enemy king. However, it can also be attained by threatening or employing duplicity to the surrendered person. But, by trusting him, the kingship and the kingdom would be endangered because there is no guarantee that the information from the surrenderer is accurate. It may be to mislead, be vigilant, or inform the enemy about the attack. Vassakara, a minister of the King Ajatashatru, devised a plan to defeat Vaishali. In this country, people are united, educated, and hard to beat by war as they follow the seven principles of Unity and Good Governance preached by Lord Gautama Buddha. According to the plan, Vassakara went to Vaishali and deceitfully made them believe that Ajatashatru punished him for advising him to avoid war on Vaishali which might cause massive destruction of human lives and resources. After some years he was serving as a judge, gained the confidence of the royal family, kindled enmity, misunderstandings

and quarrels between the people of Vaishali. Due to continuous problems among themselves, they failed to follow the seven principles of Unity and Good Governance and their strength of unity was destroyed. Then, the minister informed Ajatashatru about the right attack time, and finally Vaishali was defeated (Barua, 2020).

If a person escapes from another country and surrenders, there is no assurance that the person is really a refugee. There is a possibility of being a spy or terrorist. A Tibetan refugee Dorjee Gyaltsen spied for China in Sweden and was imprisoned in 2018. In all nations, stringent rules are followed to punish spies. In the name of Nabi Ahmed Shakir, ranked Major in the Pakistan Army, Ravindra Kaushik was imprisoned until death. Kashmir Singh, an Indian spy, was detained by Pakistan for 35 years. Strict punishments are given to the spies to ensure proper security in the nation.

Conclusion

Trusting a surrendered enemy is always risk-bearing and it is entirely imprudent to have him in one's own entourage for any reason. Whatever may be the information given by the surrendered enemy, the accuracy must be double checked before taking action. The surrendered enemy must be kept imprisoned or negotiated with the enemy country because making the enemy act freely or contact others secretly will lead to destruction like the owls slayed by an intelligent surrendered crow.

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